

SKALLDANS, AN AUDIOVISUAL IMPROVISATION FRAMEWORK

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ABSTRACT

Skalldans is an audiovisual improvisation framework for a solo laptop performer. The framework is an instrument for performance, developed in Max[2]. Sound and video syntheses are piloted with a MIDI interface, a camera, and a Wiimote; also, audiovisual streams influence each other. The present text discusses some of the hardware and software points of interest, for example, how audio and video syntheses are piloted, how the streams interact, and the camera tracking method with a linear regression stabiliser. It also touches upon the sources of inspiration for the piece.

1. INTRODUCTION

Occasionally laptop performers, stony faces lit by the computer screen and secretive to the point of incredulity, seem to demand from the audience a willing suspension of disbelief (“is he really playing or is he on Facebook?”). Live coders showcase their creative innards, perhaps mixing in a live video of their hands pecking away at the keyboard. By and large, audiences at concert events are thrilled by the body language and facial expression of performers. In the context of computer music, I felt that one way to make my laptop act more interesting was to involve myself a bit more, and to use visuals. In late 2007, I had an accident: walked straight into a glass pane and went unconscious. The doctors decided to take a MRI scan to check if the cranium was cracked (apparently it wasn’t). The bash and the scan procedure were sonically amazing experiences. I was able to get a copy of the scan data, and thought that this must be used for a performance piece. Holbein’s famous painting *The Ambassadors*, an excerpt of which is shown in Figure 1, inspired a

vanitas, a study of a skull to reflect upon the meaningless of life. Sculptures of *Shiva Tandava* suggested the idea of a dance with death (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Detail of *The Ambassadors* (Holbein, H. y., 1533), showing the skewed image of a cranium.

2. HARDWARE-SOFTWARE

Skalldans has developed over a couple of years (2008-11), in different stages of software-hardware solutions, seeking to create a responsive hybrid instrument with a ‘rich’ control [1]. The initial versions used a joystick to control the ‘dance’ of the 3D skull (see section 5, below). The problem was that this demanded at least one hand to be dedicated to piloting the visuals, which had the inconvenience of reducing the amount of control over audio. On one occasion, a second performer was engaged to control visuals only, but this was felt to be unsatisfactory. A solution was to mount a Wiimote onto a set of headphones, to capture 2 axes of head orientation: pitch (nod) and yaw (left-right turn). The Wiimote was eventually hidden in a large cap.

Figure 2. Shots from a performance of *Skalldans* at Open Ears Festival in Kortrijk, 2008, showing the ‘analog video delay’ and other visual effects. Photos by Finnbogir Péturson.

In its current version, the performer sits on stage in front of the projection screen, which allows for video feedback effects. In addition to the physical gesture capture device, control is offered by a uc33e USB MIDI interface, which has 9 sliders and 24 knobs. Figure 3 gives an overview of the flows of audio, video and control data in the framework. Processing is implemented in Max [2]. For reasons of portability, in particular to be able to run it on one computer only, syntheses are kept simple.

Figure 3. Audio, video, and control data flows.

3. AUDIO SYNTHESIS

The audio synthesis is influenced by the aesthetics of genres such as noise music and drum'n'bass. Audio synthesis and mixing are controlled by 7 sliders and 17 knobs on the uc33a interface. There are three instruments:

3.1. Drone

Two channels of additive synthesis, each with 32 oscillators, create a bass drone. The performer can adjust fundamental frequency, (in-)harmonicity, randomise phases with a keyboard click, and introduce small frequency distortions unequally to right and left channels. Figure 4 shows the Max GUI.

Figure 4. Drones with slightly inharmonic partials, illustrated by the jagged contours. In the upper part of the illustration is the Rhythm Choppers interface.

These parameters control the ‘hollowness’ of the sound and how much the stereophonic image is ‘floating’.

3.2. Coloured Noise

This instrument is created with subtractive synthesis of white noise. The skull video, down-sampled skull image yields data for two FFT filters: the left side of the image for the left-channel filter, and vice versa. See Figure 5. In parallel, there is a feedback-delay loop, to prolong the ringing of tones of ‘coloured noise’.

Figure 5. Skull image data are sampled and mapped to two FFT filters for the Noise instrument as well as for the Rhythm Choppers.

3.3. Rhythm

Two parallel ‘Reloopers’, wrapped around the “ModSquad” patcher [4], each take as input either the Drone, Coloured Noise, or a short percussion sample (Tanaka’s original “jongly”, the only non-synthesis element of the audio instrument). The ReLooper is a step sequencer, a rhythm machine that cuts up and meshes audio according to a 16-step transfer function. In *Skalldans*, the transfer function is determined by the video. As with the FFT filters, each side of the skull video frame yields data for one audio channel. The skull image is mapped onto the cut’n’mesh transformation function from the centre line and towards the edge, i.e. the left side is read ‘backwards’. This means that the ReLooper rhythms are similar just as the image is symmetric around the centre line. Since the skull will often be in the centre of the image, the first step of the ReLooper will often include the actual downbeat of the input, for example, the sample’s kick drum.

4. CAMERA TRACKING

The built-in iSight camera of my MacBook Pro was used for camera tracking of the performer's head position in 2 dimensions, left-right and up-down. The camera tracking method builds on frame differencing and 'blob' sorting [3]. Further, there is a linear regression method to improve the stability of tracking. The (x, y) positions of the 'top 5 candidate blobs' from are compared with the predicted position based on the 5 previous tracking frames, and the best match (smallest Euclidian distance) is picked. Figure 6 shows parts of the Max implementation. The system was developed for *Walking Bach Slowly* (2011), an interactive installation where 3 people were tracked simultaneously with one birds-eye camera and the system needed to be able to "lock on", e.g. to distinguish targets crossing paths.

5. VIDEO SYNTHESIS

The MRI scan of my cranium was used to create a 3D object in Maya, adding appropriate smoothing, texturing and shading. In Max (Jitter), the 3D "skull" object is mixed together with concurrent video streams: the raw camera input, the "hairpin" of the tracked performer's head, and the linear regression line, thus visualising the innards of the tracking method. Compositing effects are added in real-time.

5.1. Chromakeying and Sobel Outlining

This allows the skull to be mixed into the camera live input (treated or not). A central 'poetic' idea of the performance is to illustrate the struggle that the performer has to 'fit' the live head and the skull together. The Sobel outlining effect creates a thin outline based on connecting points of equal image contrast. See Figure 7 for an example. This effect seems to suggest the idea of how fragile the cranium is.

5.2. Compositing Effects and Video Delay

Basic VFX such as downsampling, compositing effects (cellwise multiplication, maximum, difference etc of two streams) allow the performer to make the video flow more or less abstract. An analog video delay is created by tilting the computer screen upwards so that the camera input includes what is projected onto the screen behind the performer. See Figure 2 for an example.

In earlier versions, the skull object could also be plastically transformed, e.g. flattened and stretched, much as in Holbein's painting. However, this option was eventually taken out, because it was felt that such manipulations distracted from the more subtle control enabled by simply following - albeit sometimes imperfectly - the dancing movements of the performer's head. Therefore, skull movement is now entirely piloted by the Wiimote and camera tracking, except for one slider to zoom in or out. All visual effects and mixing are piloted by 2 sliders and 4 knobs on the uc33e interface, and a few computer keys.

6. AUDIO-VISUAL INTERACTION

The skull video is downsampled, and greyscale values (alpha channel) of two rows are read into audio buffers, that will act as FFT-bin filters. The performer can select a portion of the lines that will function as amplitude modulators of the Noise and Drone instruments in order to 'chop up' a rhythm that may or may not be in synch with the Relooper rhythm machine. See Figure 5 above. A switch allows the audio of the Relooper to affect settings of the visual effects; when an amplitude threshold is crossed (hi-lo gate), a new preset is selected at random, and in this way, rhythmic alterations between VFXs follow those of the musical beat.

Figure 6. Linear regression prediction for blob tracking.

7. PERFORMING SKALLDANS

Skalldans has been included in performances in Singapore (Choppa Festival 2008), Belgium (Happy Ears 2008), see Figure 2, and Iceland (Nordic Music Days 2011), a shot from which is shown in Figure 7. Because the framework is a rather complex audiovisual instrument and still in development, these performances have been varied in expression, but the improvisation outline (the “composition”, as it were) has followed roughly the same narrative: the first section focusses on noise and details of the rather mysterious skull object; the next section reveals that it is a cranium and it starts to dance; then more musical elements are added, i.e. the Drone, eventually with rhythmic chopping; a section follows where tempo picks up and the two other video streams (live, tracking) join, in various guises; at the opportune moment, the drum’n'bass takes off and video includes more colour; towards the end, rhythms tend to synchronise and simplify while the performer ‘live head’ fuses visually with the skull; video delay is introduced, the performer stands up and dances; before the whole audio-visual thing runs into a wall - or at least, this is the feeling that I wish to convey - and the performance ends.

There would be little point in writing a score, and I prefer the piece to change from one occasion to the next. Perhaps this is the best antidote I can find to death, and

to continue dancing. Parts of the framework, in particular VFX and live mixing of video, have gone into in *Nosferatu Extemporations - The Ship* (2012), a piece for computer and saxophone. More about this can be found on my webpages [5]. Future work on the *Skalldans* improvisation framework will attempt to further improve the head (and perhaps hand) tracking with technologies such as Kinect and Leap, as well as more ways for interaction between the audio and video syntheses.

8. REFERENCES

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Figure 7. Shot from a performance of *Skalldans* at Nordic Music Days festival in Reikjavik 2011. Sobel outlining of the skull is clearly visible. Photo by Bonnie Right.